

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

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Scientific Indexing

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

ISSN (E): 2992-9148
ResearchBib Impact
Factor: 9.576 / 2024

TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN

Jaxongir Kamiljonovich Narmuminov

FOR PUBLICATION OF PAPER ENTITLED
THEME: SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI
HARAKATCHANLIGI VA HUDUDIY BANDLIK BARQARORLIGI O'RTASIDAGI
O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIKNING STATISTIK TAHLILI

17.01.2026

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FOR AN ARTICLE ON THE SUBJECT OF THEME:

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MUALLIFLIK GUVOHNOMASI

ISSN (E): 2992-9148

Ushbu guvohnoma «Technical Science Research in Uzbekistan» ilmiy jurnalining 2026-yil 01-sonida chop etilgan quyidagi ilmiy maqolaga mualliflik qilgani uchun berildi:

MAVZU: SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI HARAKATCHANLIGI VA HUDUDYIY BANDLIK BARQARORLIGI O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIKNING STATISTIK TAHLILI

Maqola qabul qilingan sana: 17.01.2026

Maqola mualliflari: Jaxongir Kamiljonovich Narmuminov

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